

Highly Twisted Double-Helix Carbon Nanotube Yarns

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1 General Introduction

The strength and flexibility of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) allow them to be constructed into a variety of innovated architectures with fascinating properties [1-6]. Here, we show that CNTs can be made into a highly twisted yarn-derived double-helix structure by a conventional twist-spinning process. The double-helix is a stable and hierarchical configuration consisting of two single-helical yarn segments, which unique mechanical properties. While one of the yarn component breaks early under tension due to the highly twisted state, the second yarn produces much larger tensile strain and significantly prolongs the process until ultimate fracture. In addition, these elastic and conductive double-helix yarns show simultaneous and reversible resistance change in response to a wide range of input sources (e.g. mechanical, optical and thermal) such as applied strains or stresses, light illumination and environmental temperature. Our results indicate that it is possible to create higher-level, more complex architectures from CNT yarns and fabricate multifunctional nanomaterials with potential applications in many areas.

2 Experimental Method

We fabricated double-helix CNT yarns by continuously spinning a single-walled nanotube film through two over-twisting steps, as illustrated in Figure 1a. The horizontally suspended CNT film was first spun into a straight yarn by an electric motor, then over-twisted into a single-helical yarn with a spiral shape, and further over-twisted into a double-helix made of two helical yarn segments. The CNTs in the initial film were random and now were aligned within the double-helix due to the strong twisting process.

Figure 1. Fabrication and characterization of double-helix CNT yarns. (a) Illustration of a spinning process. (b) Illustration of the double-helix consisting of two single-helical yarns twisted together. (c) SEM image of a long and uniform double-helix. (e) Enlarged view of the highly twisted double-helix. (f) High-magnification SEM image.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Mechanical properties analysis

We performed mechanical tests on these double-helix CNT yarns to study their fracture mechanism and energy absorption during stretching. Tension tests on more than 10 samples with different yarn diameters revealed that the two helical yarns making the double-helix always broke one after the other, with a large difference in respective tensile strains. The overall toughness could be calculated by the two areas enclosed under the two linear stages, and in general the area of stage II ($A_2 = 17\sim 26$ J/g) was larger than that of stage I ($A_1 = 7\sim 15$ J/g) for double-helices with different yarn diameters.

Figure 2. Mechanical testing on double-helix CNT yarns. (a) Illustration of the tensile testing process including two stages. (b) Load-displacement curves of two double-helices. (c) Illustration of the tensile strengths, strains, areas under each loading stage. (d) Calculated areas (toughness) under the loading curves at two stages.

3.2 Electrical properties analysis

Our multifunctional double-helix CNT yarns were elastic and electrically conductive, with clear response to various sources such as mechanical strain, and environmental temperature.

Figure 3. Properties and potential applications of CNT double-helix CNT yarns (a) Tensile load-time curve. (b) Recorded yarn resistance change during repeated stress cycles. (c) Illustration of a double-helix configured as a thermocouple to sense the temperature (T) increase in a heat source. (d) Resistance values recorded in three different double-helix yarns during temperature increase from 40 to 120 °C.

The resistance was measured through the entire yarn length (L) from one end to the other end of the double-helix. Three samples with different yarn diameters and lengths all displayed similar linear behavior in this temperature range, with calculated slopes in the range of 0.08 to 0.14 $\Omega/^\circ\text{C}$ (Fig. 3c, d). The results indicated that heating at the tip could effectively change the resistance through the double-helix, and unexpectedly, producing a linear R-T relationship.

In conclusion, we adopted a simple and controllable method to produce double-helix CNT yarns with neat structure and distinct two-stage fracture behavior, which would be important for designing structures to prevent catastrophic failure. These double-helix structures demonstrated potential applications as strain sensors, optical detectors and thermocouple-like devices. Given the mechanical strength, and flexibility of CNT yarns, there is a great promise to fabricate hierarchical and more complex architectures and to explore their applications in many areas such as sensors, actuators, fiber-shape devices and electrodes.

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